

MEDICAL SCIENCES

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ АМЕБНОГО АБСЦЕССА ПЕЧЕНИ

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COMPARATIVE FEATURES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF AMOEBIC LIVER ABSCESS

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Аннотация

В статье рассмотрены сравнительные особенности хирургического лечения амёбного абсцесса. 48 пациентов с амёбным абсцессом печени (АЛП) были оценены в сравнительном, проспективном и рандомизированном исследовании лечения АЛП. В исследование были включены взрослые пациенты с абсцессом правой доли печени и диаметром абсцесса от 4 до 12 см. Бактериальные абсцессы были исключены микробиологическим исследованием абсцессной жидкости у всех больных. 19 пациентов лечили только метронидазолом в течение 10 дней, а 29 больным под лапароскопическим и ультразвуковым контролем с аспирацией жидкости из абсцесса дополнительно к введению препарата проводили пунктирование. Клинические симптомы лихорадки, боли в правом подреберье и болезненности печени, лабораторные показатели СОЭ, лейкоцитов, гемоглобина и С-реактивного белка, размер абсцесса определяли в день поступления и наблюдали в течение периода наблюдения 38 дней. Улучшение болезненности печени было значительно быстрее в группе аспирации в течение первых 3 дней ($P < 0,001$), тогда как все остальные параметры не показали различий между двумя группами. Этого незначительного преимущества явно недостаточно, чтобы оправдать рутинную пункционную аспирацию и выступает в поддержку только медикаментозного лечения неосложненных амёбных абсцессов печени диаметром до 12 см, расположенных в правой доле печени.

Abstract

The article deals with comparative features of surgical treatment of amoebic abscess. 48 patients with Amoebic Liver Abscess (ALA) were evaluated in a comparative, prospective and randomized study for the treatment of ALA. Adult patients with an abscess located in the right liver lobe and an abscess diameter of 4 to 12 cm were included. Bacterial abscesses were excluded by microbiological examination of abscess fluid in all patients. 19 patients were treated with metronidazole for 10 days alone and 29 patients were punctured under Laparoscopic and ultrasound guidance with aspiration of abscess fluid in addition to drug administration. The clinical symptoms fever, pain in right upper abdomen and liver tenderness, and the laboratory parameters erythrocyte sedimentation rate, white blood cells, haemoglobin and C-reactive protein and the abscess size were determined on the day of admission and followed during an observation period of 38 days. Improvement of liver tenderness was significantly faster in the aspiration group during the first 3 days ($P < 0.001$), whereas all the other parameters showed no differences between the two groups. This minor benefit is obviously not sufficient to justify routine needle aspiration and advocates drug treatment alone for uncomplicated amoebic liver abscesses with a diameter up to 12 cm located in the right liver lobe.

Ключевые слова: амёбы, абсцесс печени, пункция, жидкость, препарат, гемоглобин, амёбиаз.

Keywords: amoebic, liver abscess, puncture, fluid, drug, haemoglobin, ameobiasis.

Amoebiasis is an antroponurosis invasion infected (transmitted) with faecal-oral mechanism. According to the data by World Health Organization (WHO), up to 10% of the people living in the world are suffering from amoebiasis.

The second fatal disease caused by parasitic diseases in the world, is amoebic dysentery, which creates amoebic abscess by hitching with blood from the intestinal wall passing into the liver. Asian and South American countries are considered to be endemic areas [1]. They can often be found in hot countries. In developed

countries, the prevalence is recorded in tourists and emigrants from endemic regions. Due to some literature, there is a very high mortality rate of amoebic liver abscess which is up to 70-80% [2]. According to drug treatment is effective in cases with abscess size of 5cm or less. With abscesses larger than 5 cm in diameter, minimally invasive methods are much more effective and profitable along with drugs. [3, p.122]. The drainage catheter procedures are recommended only after 48-72 hours of clinical signs. The only source of infection is the individual with amoebiasis or an amoebic carrier. Furthermore, the disease can pass via fecal-oral

route in case the infected cysts of water, fresh vegetables and salads are consumed. The disease is transmitted as a result of direct contact. Moreover, cysts can be spread by cockroaches (the insects) and flies. Cysts can survive for 2-4 weeks in warm, humid environment. Amoebic liver abscess usually happens in odds, the size is of a large volume, the frequent location is in the right lobe of liver. Abscess contents are in the form of thick liquid which looks like anchovy paste - and small fish paste like herring, and is red-and-khaki (brown) [4, p.66].

The goal of the study is to improve the effectiveness of treatments of patients by comparatively learning the effectiveness of traditional and non-invasive treatments of amoebic liver abscess.

The research included forty-eight patients with amoebic liver abscess during the years of 2010-2021 in Radiology Department Head Office of Kocaeli University Research and Implementation Hospital in the Republic of Turkey, Scientific Surgery Center named after academic M.A.Topchubashov, Azerbaijan, as well as Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic Hospital, Azerbaijan.

35 (72.9%) patients were men and 13 (27.1%) were women out of 48 patients aged 16-78. The average age was 32.4 ± 14.4 years old. 19 (39.6%) patients with 24 amoebic abscess were treated with traditional methods, while 29 (60,4%) patients with 38 amoebic abscess

were interfered with non-invasive ultrasound, CT, R-Scope and Laparoscopic methods.

Amoebic liver abscess is characterized by general weakness, fatigue, liver enlargement (hepatomegaly) ($p < 0.001$), pain in the region of localization, hectic or fixed-type high temperature (up to 39°C), fever, chills, night sweats. The positive and negative predictive values of biochemical analysis, sensitivity, anemia, and the characteristics were respectively 96.5%, 61.36%, 83% and 90%. Right lobe preference odd abscess was observed in 87.2% of cases.

Diagnosis of amoebiasis: The clinic, laboratory treatments of the disease are based on the results of general and biochemical blood tests, liver function test, and serological tests for amoebiasis, reactions (RIF, PCK, IFA examinations, hemagglutination) and rentgenology, ultrasound, CT, NMR tests.

Serological tests are positive in 95% of the patients with extraintestinal amebiasis. Intestinal amebiasis in children, in most cases, intoxication obviously reveals itself. Thus, the temperature rises up to $38 - 39^{\circ}\text{C}$, accompanied by drowsiness, nausea, sickness and vomiting. Expelling of liquid and porridge-like feces accompanied by large amounts of mucus, the frequency of the act of defecation is 10-15 times during a day, there is also the possibility of dehydration. During large abscesses, jaundice may occur, it is considered to be a Pius prognostic sign.

Figure 1: Ultrasound image of Amoebic Liver Abscess in the right lobe.

Figure 2: CT scan of numerous amoebic liver abscesses.

Discussion of the results: In the recent past, amoebic liver abscesses were managed surgically in exceptional cases. However, nowadays, conservative and noninvasive abscesses are overcome with percutaneous

needle and with percutaneous catheter for percutaneous-catheterization-drainage (PCD) under the control of ultrasound, CT, laparoscopic control or aspiration.

Figure 3: Percutaneous catheter for percutaneous-catheterization-drainage (PCD) under the control of ultrasound, CT, laparoscopic control or aspiration.

The use of continuous drainage catheter has been widespread and it is considered safe and effective method when applied with conservative treatment [5]. 19 (39.6%) patients were cured from 24 amoebic abscesses with traditional methods; 29 (60.4%) patients were cured from 38 amoebic abscesses with noninvasive ultrasound, CT and laparoscopic control catheter drainage under control PCD. PCD beginning from the first time ($n = 26$), second time ($N = 9$) and third time ($n = 3$) were carried noninvasive procedures. 10 F percutaneous aspiration biopsy and 12 F PCD were successfully realized in abscesses with the diameter of 50 mm or less than 10 F. In the initial stage, all randomized patients were treated with intravenous 100 mg of Metronidazole injection 3 times a day. Along with Metronidazole treatment in amoebic liver abscess, Xiniophon (Yatren), diiodoxin, mexasform, intestopan and other

drugs are used. These drugs are sometimes used together with surgical treatment.

The drugs used for Conservative treatment can be divided into 2 groups: "associated (contacted)" or "perforated" (which affects the form of the perforated form of intestine) and systemic tissue amoebocytes. Perforated amoebocytes are used for the treatment of amoebiasis (of asymptomatic "carriers"). Perforated amoebocytes are also used to prevent the recurrence. In order to treat amoebiasis, mainly metronidazole or tinidazole is used, as an alternative scheme the tetracycline group is used. Tips to azinvasive methods are the large size of amoebic abscess (over 5 cm), the placement of amoebic abscess in the right or left share, or in the upper part of the liver, in case of tension danger in the abdominal wall because of abscess explosion, the ineffectiveness of conservative treatment within 48 hours. When closed

drainage cannot be carried out, when abscess explodes (disperses), and peritonitis develops, open operative treatment is carried out. Laparoscopic surgery is widely used in recent years.

Laparoscopic surgery was carried out on 13 (27.1%) patients out of 48 patients in the scientific research. The laparoscopic peritoneum toileting is very effective and efficient method; it has a lot of further advantages. Pneumoperitoneum protects the laparoscopic

toileting peritoneum, from internal abdominal complications and unpleasant consequences (of abdominal cavity) in advance. Amoebic abscess is observed with 20 % of bacterial infection, 5-10% of jaundice, 2-5% of peritonitis. The following complications were registered in the treatment process of treatment and control groups of patients: bleeding, drainage (movement) migration, peritonitis, septic and bile flows, Pleural empyema, soft tissue phlegmon, and other.

Figure 4. The ultrasound image after 48 hours of laparoscopic surgery.

Figure 5.

The scar shrinkage of the residual cavity after 3 months of laparoscopic surgeries was indicated by an arrow.

Thus, amoebic liver abscesses are more likely to recover within 1-3 weeks after surgery. The results obtained from the both groups were scientifically analyzed. The effectiveness indicators of the carried treatment were determined with the analysis of disease history and clinical, laboratory, anamnestic, CT, ultrasound and X-ray studies. Criteria for successful treatment are focal lesion scarring, CT and ultrasound

screening, loss or a significant reduction of abscess cavity.

The scar shrinkage of the residual cavity in amoebic liver abscess performed under the ultrasound image after 3 months of laparoscopic surgeries was indicated by an arrow.

Prognosis: is good.

Table-1.

Results	According to the groups				Evaluations
	Control (n=19)		Main (n=29)		
	Sayı	%	Sayı	%	
Recovery	9	47,4	21	72,4	Good
Complication	8	42,1	7	24,1	Satisfactory
Recidive	2	10,5	1	3,4	Unsatisfactory
Death		0	0	0	Bad

As seen from the table, abscess cavity (after proper procedures) were fully absorbed in 21 cases (72.4%) out of the main group of 29 patients, the treatment was successfully completed in 9 cases (47,4,0%) in the control group of 19 patients. The results are good. More than 50% of abscess cavity was observed with a number of complications and shrinking in 8 (42.1%) patients within the control group, while in the main group 7 cases (24.1%). The result is satisfactory. Less than 50% of abscess cavity reduced and decreased in 1 case (3.4%) of the main group, 2 cases (10.5%) of the control group patients, that is, it caused a recurrence. The result is unsatisfactory. Death was observed neither in the main nor in the control group.

All patients with amoebiasis must be hospitalized. Isolation and treatment of patients are carried out till a complete clinical recovery. Patients, who are healthy carriers of cysts and cavities, are not allowed to work in the nutrition system, food products industry. Damage center is disinfected. Preventive measures should be taken against collateral gastrointestinal infections.

In case of repeated illness, patients should be under control by a dispensary for 12 months. They must pass medical and laboratory examinations every 3 months. Patients infected with amoebiasis in food and

catering organizations should be under dispensary control until the amoebiasis reproductive is completely resolved by sanitation.

Consequently, azinvasive surgical interventions are highly effective treatment methods in amoebic liver abscesses. The efficiency in the treatment of amoebic liver abscesses form 96.8% - 90.4%.

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